

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

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THE ROLE OF SMART MANUFACTURING IN COST REDUCTION AND LABOR MARKET TRANSFORMATION

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Abstract: In this article, the author discusses smart and autonomous manufacturing systems that are being implemented to improve production processes. Having analyzed research papers, the article summarizes whether technological innovation supports the minimization of production costs and its effects on the labor market.

Key words: Autonomous, smart factories, manufacturing system, Artificial Intelligence, software, robots, Internet of Things.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ishlab chiqarish jarayonini takomillashtirish maqsadida qo'llanilayotgan "smart", o'z-o'zini boshqaruvchi tizim haqida ma'lumotlar beriladi. Qilinayotgan ilmiy ishlar asosida ishlab chiqarish sektoridagi ushbu innovatsion yangilik mehnat bozori va ishlab chiqarish xarajatlarini minimallashtirishga qanchalik ko'mak berayotganligi yoritib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Avtonom, aqlli fabrikalar, ishlab chiqarish tizimi, sun'iy intellekt, dastur, robot, Internet vositalari.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена информация о "умных" самоуправляемых системах, применяемых с целью совершенствования производственных процессов. На основе проведённых научных исследований раскрывается, как данное инновационное решение в производственном секторе способствует минимизации затрат на производство и снижению влияния на рынок труда.

Ключевые слова: автономные, умные фабрики, производственная система, искусственный интеллект, программное обеспечение, роботы, интернет-ресурсы.

INTRODUCTION

Many years ago, labor used to be the main factor in the production process. With advancements in technology, the manufacturing process began to undergo automation through machines programmed by humans. However, the revolution in production processes has recently advanced so rapidly that manufacturing companies now operate without the need for human intervention, using smart factories and autonomous manufacturing systems.

It is important to emphasize that, from one standpoint, such cutting-edge technology helps reduce production costs and waste. However, from another standpoint, it has a significant impact on the current labor market in the manufacturing sector.

Although there have been numerous studies on the terms “smart and autonomous factories,” and many definitions have been proposed, their clear meanings are still not fully explained. As many aspects of technology remain undiscovered, there is still room to learn more about the terms “smart and autonomous” in the manufacturing context.

METHODOLOGY

The research for this thesis was conducted using secondary research, which involves collecting and analyzing published data, information, and resources. This method was chosen for its efficiency in gathering diverse information from reliable sources, such as academic articles, books, industry reports, and authoritative websites. Secondary research is advantageous for exploring existing knowledge on a topic, establishing a comprehensive understanding of the subject, and offering a broad perspective on the research questions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The data for this study were primarily gathered from the following sources. **Academic Journals and Books:** Articles and books focusing on smart and autonomous manufacturing systems, Industry 4.0, and their impact on production processes were reviewed. These sources provided detailed insights into theoretical frameworks, industry practices, and technological advancements. **Industry Reports and White Papers:** Reports from leading industry organizations, such as McKinsey & Company, Deloitte, and other research institutes, were analyzed. These reports offered valuable data on trends, cost reduction strategies, and real-world applications of smart manufacturing technologies. **Websites and Online Databases:** Reputable websites, including academic databases (e.g., ScienceDirect, Springer), government publications, and corporate websites, were consulted. These sources provided supplementary case studies, current industry trends, and examples of companies implementing smart and autonomous manufacturing systems.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Smart factories are at the core of technological transformation, referred to as Industry 4.0. They are characterized by the use of recent technological innovations to enhance production quality and efficiency. Each component of the technology contributes to an accurate manufacturing process [1].

Employing sensors and software enables factories to collect and disseminate data during the entire manufacturing process. For a better understanding of the case, Tesla Automotive company serves as an example of implementing smart systems in car manufacturing. Sensors are installed on machines and assembly lines during the production of car parts. These sensors monitor aspects such as temperature, pressure, machine speed, and product quality. In the event of an issue, such as inefficient speed or a broken part of the assembly line, the sensors detect the problem [3].

The use of data plays a crucial role in a central software system that analyzes it in real time. If issues like machine overheating or defects on the line are identified, the system either alerts factory managers or automatically fixes the defect to prevent further errors. Additionally, the software can disseminate data to inventory management systems to verify the availability of materials in stock.

Implementing artificial intelligence and machine learning in the manufacturing sector unlocks a million opportunities for companies. These emerging trends stand out by enabling robotic production lines, quality control, supply chain optimization, and predictive maintenance.

Tesla's artificial intelligence strategy emphasizes the use of AI-powered robots in its manufacturing lines to perform tasks such as painting, assembling, and material handling. AI enables robots to adjust their speed according to feedback from the production line. More precisely, robotic arms can automatically adjust their speed based on the specific part being assembled [2].

Tesla also leverages AI and machine learning to predict customer demand by analyzing market demands, sales history, and market trends. This allows the company to minimize the risk of surplus or insufficient production. Additionally, AI contributes to optimizing supply chain operations by reducing the risk of excess inventory costs and material waste. It achieves this by forecasting the required parts and materials for upcoming production runs [2].

Although smart and autonomous factories share similarities, it is important to highlight the differences between them. Autonomous factories represent a more advanced version of smart factories, eliminating the need for human assistance in production lines. As predicted a million years ago, when the possibility of robots replacing human labor was envisioned, this concept has become a reality in autonomous manufacturing. This stage incorporates AI, the Internet of Things (IoT), data, software, robots, sensors, automated management systems, and self-quality control.

In contrast, smart manufacturing systems rely on limited human intervention, where human input is still an integral part of the process.

Researching the concept and differences between smart and autonomous manufacturing systems, findings indicate that both systems can be implemented on the production line simultaneously.

The primary objective of any entrepreneur is to reduce costs without compromising the quality of products or services. Running a business with minimal cost or waste leads to better cash flow, higher profits, and opportunities to invest in business growth. Research conducted by McKinsey with 24 industrial companies in 2020 revealed that smart and autonomous manufacturing systems could reduce indirect costs by as much as 15–20% within 12–18 months [4].

Wu and Wilson (2022) mentioned that integrating traditional business models with the Internet is considered a stepping stone to achieving efficient cost management and optimal resource allocation [5].

Research findings by Chen and Xu (2023) showed that cost stickiness through enhanced technology remains consistent, provided that employees possess a high level of expertise and the enterprises are non-state-owned.

The concept of cost stickiness refers to the phenomenon where manufacturing companies, when experiencing a surge in production demand, immediately invest in additional employees and raw materials to increase production shifts. However, in cases of a sudden drop in demand, they cannot directly reduce costs due to factors such as employment contracts and excess inventory (Anderson, Banker, & Janakiraman, 2003) [5]. Proactive approaches, such as implementing smart systems, can be used to mitigate cost stickiness.

An excellent demonstration of this concept is Siemens' implementation of its Amberg Electronic Plants in Germany. Siemens successfully established an automated production line where machines interact with each other and a centralized control system. The plant produces programmable logic controllers, leveraging data analytics and machine learning to forecast potential machine failures, schedule maintenance, and reduce downtime. This approach has significantly increased productivity and reduced production costs [6].

At Amberg, the company consistently trains artificial intelligence to perform zero-error operations. Consequently, the need for costly and time-consuming X-ray tests for quality assurance could be eliminated, as these tests are considered a bottleneck in the manufacturing process. If Siemens completes this mission, it could reduce capital investment by €500,000 [7].

Since the outbreak of the Industrial Revolution, humanity has experienced four rounds of technological revolution, with each change reflecting the deepening of automation technology. In the process of replacing humans with machines, conflicts and rebalancing between efficiency and employment have been consistently observed (Liu 2018; Morgan 2019) [8].

Michau (2013), Josifidis and Supic (2018), and Forsythe (2022) mentioned that as humanity experiences new waves of technological development, it must also accept the dual nature of “creative destruction” accompanying these advancements.

Here, the term “creative destruction,” coined by economist Joseph Schumpeter, refers to how technological changes alter the roles of ordinary, unskilled workers by employing machines embedded with the Internet of Things (IoT) and artificial intelligence (AI) [8]. The revolution of the economic system, driven by innovation and adaptation in technological transformation, has reshaped the nature of employment, including career pathways, employment forms, and occupational skill requirements.

Research conducted in the UK by the Tony Blair Institute for Global Change estimated that efficient integration of AI by UK companies could save nearly a quarter of the time spent by 6 million employees. Annually, job displacement ranged between 60,000 and 275,000 jobs in the UK [9].

To clarify the phenomenon, let's examine the case involving Foxconn, a Taiwanese multinational electronics manufacturing company and a major supplier to global tech giants like Apple, Sony, and Microsoft. Established in 1974 by Terry Gou, Foxconn operates numerous branches in countries such as China, India, Vietnam, the USA, and Mexico.

While adapting automation in its production lines, Foxconn has significantly boosted efficiency in manufacturing by replacing 60,000 factory workers with robots. The Foxconn Technology Group confirmed that their operations are increasingly reliant on robots due to their smart manufacturing system. However, they denied triggering long-term job losses. The company emphasized that robotics are being adapted for repetitive tasks previously done by humans, while a workforce is still required for value-added tasks such as research and development, quality control, and process control [10].

Economists have raised concerns about the impact of automation on the labor market. Research conducted by Deloitte Group in collaboration with Oxford University estimates that up to 35% of jobs are at risk over the next 20 years.

A practical solution to the unemployment challenges posed by automated manufacturing systems could be upskilling and reskilling programs. Emerging technologies are creating new roles in fields such as data

analytics, robotics, and programming. Unskilled workers should be sponsored by companies or governments to receive training aligned with industry needs. Encouraging workers to acquire hybrid skills—combining technical knowledge with problem-solving and critical thinking—through massive online platforms is an effective way to retain employees within companies.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, this analysis highlights those developments in information technology have significantly reduced manufacturing costs, resulting in higher profits for companies. However, it has also caused high unemployment due to the replacement of human tasks with robots. If necessary, measures are considered before implementing smart systems on production lines, the risks of high unemployment might not materialize in the economic scenario.

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